

A new species of the subfamily Phycitinae from French Guyana (Lepidoptera : Pyralidae).

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- **Abstract.** A new species is described within the American genus *Psorosina* Dyar (subfamily Phycitinae): *Psorosina bernardfrancoisi* **n. sp.** This species is the third known in this genus of which it is the first record in Southern America. It is currently endemic to French Guiana.
- **Résumé. Une nouvelle espèce de la sous-famille des Phycitinae décrite de Guyane Française (Lepidoptera : Pyralidae).** Une espèce nouvelle est décrite dans le genre américain *Psorosina* Dyar (sous-famille des Phycitinae) : *Psorosina bernardfrancoisi* **sp. nov.** Cette espèce est la troisième connue dans ce genre, et la première en Amérique du Sud. Elle semble à ce jour connue seulement de Guyane Française.
- **Key-words.** Pyraloidea, Phycitinae, new species, Guyana, French Guiana, South America, Neotropical area, systematics.
- **Mots-clefs.** Pyraloidea, Phycitinae, espèce nouvelle, Guyane, Guyane française, Amérique du Sud, région néotropicale, systématique.

Introduction

The study of the historical Neotropical Phycitinae collection of the Paris Natural History Museum (MNHN) and the recent transmission of newly collected insects from Guyana by Mr. Bernard François lead me to evidence the presence in French Guiana of an previously undetermined species of the *Ancylosis* complex of genera. Two individuals have been found, both males, in two different places.

Material and methods

Imago are preserved within the Microlepidoptera collection of the Paris Museum (General collection – Neotropical collection).

Genitalia slides have been prepared by then author, coloured with Chlorazol-E black and preserved in Euparal balm; slides have been deposited within the Guillaume Leraut's slides collections (UMR 7205, Lepidoptera slides collection).

The nomenclature follows LERAUT (2021) updated by LERAUT (2022 b).

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Results

This species appears as being quite atypical compared to other Phycitinae from Guyana. Male genitalia have typical features: a broad, straight aedeagus with a long and robust acicular cornutus, conical uncus, short and broad gnathos, long and broad vinculum, valvae with a robust costa.

Amongst American genera, such features correspond to the genus *Psorosina* DYAR, 1904: 113 despite a fairly different habitus (but the external appearance is not a good criterion for distinguishing Phycitinae). Male genitalia of the type species of *Psorosina* Dyar, *P. hammondi* (Riley, 1872) (= *angulella* Dyar, 1904), are illustrated by HEINRICH (1956: 417, n°461), and those of *P. hammondi* Blanchard & Knudson, 1983 from Texas by their authors (BLANCHARD & KNUDSON, 1983: 220).

This genus appears closely related to the genera *Ancyloysis* Zeller, 1839 (the latter with a shorter vinculum and a thin aedeagus), *Cabotia* Ragonot, 1888 (often considered as synonym to *Ancyloysis*; aedeagus without any cornutus, gnathos broad and rounded, saccus truncated), *Honora* Grote, 1878 (transtilla broad and quite short, aedeagus with a thin cornutus), *Honorinus* Heinrich, 1956 (male very similar to *Honora*), *Oncolabis* Zeller, 1848 (with a thin spicle-like digitation on the anal edge of the valvae and thin cornuti within the aedeagus) or either *Eurythmasis* Dyar, 1914 (valvae narrow, gnathos thin and straight, vinculum broad and truncated saccus).

This species seems not being already described in America, especially in the Neotropical areas (HEINRICH, 1956; NEUNZIG, 2003; NEUNZIG & DOW, 1993; NEUNZIG & SOLIS, 2002 a; 2002 b; 2004; NUÑEZ & BARRO CAÑAMERO, 2012; LERAUT, 2022 a; SOLIS, NEUNZIG & LARA, 2023). Thus, I provide its description below:

Psorosina bernardfrancoisi G. Leraut, n. sp. (Fig. 1-2)

Derivatio nominis. Neutral name. Dedicated to my estimated colleague Bernard François (Société Entomologique de France, Paris) who found the second specimen of the present species.

Holotype. 1 male, French Guiana, Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni, without date, coll. L. & J. de Joannis (1920-1932), prep. G. Leraut n°966, coll. générale, MNHN, Paris.

Paratype. 1 male, French Guiana, Saül, “devant l’aérodrome, aérogare” [Saül airport], 12-X-2002 (« F754 »), rec. B. François, coll. G. Leraut, prep. G. Leraut n°1110, MNHN, Paris.

Diagnosis. *Habitus* (**Fig. 1 a-b**). Wingspan 12 mm. Antenna simple, pubescent ; sinus small. Maxillary palpi thin, without aigrette. Wings: antemedial line faint, white, slightly sinuous, margined outwardly by a brownish shadow. Subterminal line conspicuous, white, slightly outwardly angled near middle; margined inwardly with a thin brown line, outwardly with fainter, diffuse, brownish line. Discal dots greyish brown, faint, separate. Terminal line brown. Fringe fuscous. Hindwing: Fuscous, lighter toward base. Brown terminal line. Fringe fuscous. Body greyish brown.

Genitalia (**Fig. 2 a-b**). Uncus hoodlike, apex rounded; apical process of gnathos a slender hook; transtilla rudimentary; heavily sclerotized costa with a basal projection; juxta with lateral lobes;

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vinculum oblong, longer than broad, V-shaped; aedeagus trapeze-shaped, moderately short, broad, armed with one single strong spine-like cornutus.

Biology. Unknown. Tropical forest. Currently known only from French Guiana, but presumably not restricted to this area: to be searched for in the Guyana Shield.

Remark. Collecting the female of this species would help reasserting its belonging to the genus *Psorosina*.

Figure 1 a-b. *Psorosina bernardfrancoisi* G. Leraut, **n. sp.**, holotype, male (a: habitus, b: labels).

Figure 2 a-b. *Psorosina bernardfrancoisi* G. Leraut, **n. sp.**, holotype, male, genitalia (a: armature, b: aedeagus), prep. G. Leraut n°966.

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References

- BLANCHARD, André & KNUDSON, Edward C., 1983.** - A new species of *Psorosina* Dyar (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) from Texas. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, **85** (3): 619-621.
- DYAR, Georges D., 1904.** - Additions to the list of North American Lepidoptera, N°2. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, **6** (2): 103-117.
- HEINRICH, Carl, 1956.** - *American Moths of the Subfamily Phycitinae*. Bulletin of the United States National Museum eds., p. 1-581, 1138 figures.
- LERAUT, Guillaume H.-C. 2021.** - *Spécies général des Phycitinae – A global comprehensive check-list of the Phycitinae (Lep.: Pyraloidea, Pyralidae)*. Revue Française d'Entomologie Générale eds., supplement to tome **2** (5-6), p. 1-372, index [p. 373-472], fig. 1-65, Autun.
- LERAUT, Guillaume H.-C. 2022 a.** - Description of a new species of Pyralid moth from French Guiana (Lepidoptera, Phycitinae). *Revue Française d'Entomologie Générale*, **4** (9): 265-269.
- LERAUT, Guillaume H.-C. 2022 b.** - Addendum et corrigendum au Spécies général des Phycitinae (Lepidoptera, Pyraloidea) (I). *Revue Française d'Entomologie Générale*, **4** (9): 275-282.
- NEUNZIG, Herbert H. 2003.** - Pyraloidea, Pyralidae (part), Phycitinae (part). - In **DOMINICK, R. B. et alii**, *The Moths of America north of Mexico*, **15** (5): 1-338, Allen Press, Inc., Lawrence, Kansas.
- NEUNZIG, Herbert H. & DOW, L. C. 1993.** - The Phycitinae of Belize (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). *North Carolina Agricultural Research Service Technical Bulletin*, **304**: i-iv, 1-131, Raleigh.
- NEUNZIG, Herbert H. & SOLIS, Alma, 2002 a.** - The *Ceracanthia* complex (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae: Phycitinae) in Costa Rica. I. *Ceracanthia* Ragonot. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, **104** (4): 837-855.
- NEUNZIG, Herbert H. & SOLIS, Alma, 2002 b.** - The *Ceracanthia* complex (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae: Phycitinae) in Costa Rica. II. *Megarthria* Ragonot, *Drescoma* Dyar and *Lascelina* Heinrich. *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, **104** (4): 980-992.
- NEUNZIG, Herbert H. & SOLIS, Alma, 2004.** - *Exguiana*, a new genus of neotropical phycitines (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, **106** (3): 554-563.
- NUÑEZ, Rayner & BARRO CAÑAMERO, Alejandro, 2012.** - A list of Cuban Lepidoptera (Arthropoda: Insecta). *Zootaxa*, **3384**: 1-59.

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SOLIS, Alma ; NEUNZIG, Herbert H. & LARA, Manuel Balcazár, 2023. -Phycitinae (Pyraloidea: Pyralidae) of the Sierra Tarahumara Region in Northwestern Mexico. *Journal of the Lepidopterists' Society*, **77** (3): 143-158 - DOI: 10.18473/lepi.77i3.a2

ZELLER, Philipp Christoph, 1839. - Versuch einer naturgemäßen Eintheilung der Schaben. *Isis, oder encyclopädische Zeitung von Oken*, **32** (3): 167-219, Leipzig.

Online references

GlobIZ. - Nuss, M., B. Landry, R. Mally, F. Vegliante, A. Tränkner, F. Bauer, J. Hayden, A. Segerer, R. Schouten, H. Li, T. Trofimova, M. A. Solis, J. De Prins & W. Speidel, [2003–2022], *Global Information System on Pyraloidea*. - www.pyraloidea.org [last accessed 30/11/2022].

Moths Photographers Group. – Nanz, Steve et alii, North American Moth Photographers Group at the Mississippi Entomological Museum at Mississippi State University – *A digital guide to moth identification*. <http://mothphotographersgroup.msstate.edu> [last accessed 20/12/2022].

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